

Open eScience Call 2025 (OEC 2025)

Full Proposal

Introduction

Please refer to the Call for Proposals “Open eScience Call (OEC 2025)” for the Terms and Conditions of this granting scheme. The call text is available at <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals/>

The proposal should be written in English. The layout of the proposal should facilitate easy reading. Use the Verdana font size 8 or similar.

Proposals must be submitted as a PDF using the ConFTool submission system available at <https://www.conftool.org/escience/>. The proposal must be submitted from the personal account of the Lead Applicant.

The deadline for submission is **13 October 2025, 14:00 CET**

For more information, please check <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals/> or contact:

Programme Office Netherlands eScience Center

Email: open-calls@esciencecenter.nl

Telephone: +31 (0)20 460 4770

All blue italic text contains instructions. This text may be deleted before submission.

1. Lead Applicant

The LA is the contact person for all correspondence.

Name, first name, title(s):	...
Gender:	...
Position:	...
Contract end date (if applicable)	...
Organization:	...
Faculty / Department / Section	...
Email address:	...
Telephone number:	...
Postal address:	...
Postal code and City:	...

2. Research Team

The proposal must be submitted by an LA representing a Research Team. The objective of the Research Team is to support the execution of the project proposal according to the agreed project plan. At least one Research Team member must be an active researcher based at a research-performing organization other than that of the LA. Even though team members other than the LA are not required to specify their contribution to the project, doing so will help to establish the commitment of the team.

Public-private collaborations are possible, but the inclusion of industrial partners in the Research Team is not required.

Note that the requested RSEs will be allocated by the eScience Center.

Name	Affiliation	Position	Contribution (FTE)	Expertise & type of involvement
Lead Applicant			at least 0.1 required	
Co-applicant / Team member			no requirement	
Co-applicant / Team member			no requirement	
eScience Center RSE (unnamed)			requested	
eScience Center RSE (unnamed)			requested	
Add/remove as many rows as required				

3. Title and Abbreviation

A short and specific title for the proposed research. Please also specify an abbreviation for the project title (for instance an acronym).

Title: ...
Abbreviation: ...

4. Summary for the eScience Center website (max. 150 words)

Please provide a non-expert summary of the proposal for use on the eScience Center website and other media. This summary will be made public only in case the proposal is awarded. The eScience Center reserves the right to edit the text for reasons of consistency, correctness, formatting or otherwise.

...

5. Research area

Indicate exactly one research area for the proposal. In case the research fits more than one areas, please select the most appropriate one. Submitted proposals compete within the selected research area only.

- Life Sciences
- Natural Sciences and Engineering
- Social Sciences and Humanities
- Environment and Sustainability

6. Link with eScience expertise

Indicate the area(s) of expertise the proposed work is expected to require. In case your research does not exactly match one of the options, but you are of the opinion that your project idea still fits well within the aims and scope of the call, please direct your questions in a timely fashion to open-calls@esciencecenter.nl

- Software quality: workflow technologies, software practices, software sustainability, optimization
- AI: machine learning, AI image processing, Natural Language Processing, responsible AI
- Analytics: big data analytics, text and image analysis, visualization
- Data processing: accessible and searchable data, real-time data analysis, interoperability
- Computing: hardware accelerators, high-performance computing, cloud computing combining simulations

7. Project proposal (max 7 A4 pages for 7a – 7c)

The text and optional illustrations should facilitate easy reading and should be self-contained. References are allowed and can be listed under Section 7d. In case there is an overlap with the software management plan (SMP), refer to that plan for details.

- 7a. Research idea

Describe the research problem you are planning to work on and pose a concise research question following from that problem. Provide context for the importance of the problem being solved. Please describe:

- *the research problem, the research question and the scientific approach*
- *the project's objectives*
- *at least one concrete use case*
- *the efforts within the broader research community to address the methodological issue at hand*

...

- 7b. eScience and technological challenges

Describe the advantages of new eScience solutions in relation to the current state of the art in your discipline, with regard to your research topic. Describe how a project with the eScience Center could address the methodological issue and research idea discussed in Section 7a. Software and/or data on which the project depends should be described briefly here and extensively in Section 9. Please describe:

- *what are the current digital technology and methodology of choice? What are their limitations? Why do they not suffice to answer the research question posed in Section 7a?*
- *which technological and/or methodological challenges need to be overcome to reach the aims described in Section 7a?*
- *how will working with the eScience Center address the methodological issues and research idea described in Section 7a?*
- *if there is existing data and/or software on which this project depends, please relate the challenges described here to the data and/or software listed in Section 9 or in the SMP*

...

- 7c. Software sustainability and impact

Describe how the software developed in this project will be made sustainable and what the expected impact will be. If a part of this is already covered by your SMP, you can refer to that in this text. Please describe:

- *how the technology and software will find use beyond the proposed work itself, preferably across institutional, national or disciplinary borders, both during and after the finalization of the project*
- *how the technological and software deliverables will be made open source/open access and permit use and/or interpretation by other researchers*
- *how long-term maintenance and sustainability of project results (in particular software and data) will be secured and managed*
- *which efforts are made to promote the results of the project, in terms of both academic publications and the formation of a research community around the software (through demonstrations, posters, presentations, workshops, training, etc)*
- *the topic(s) for the obligatory workshop, indicate in what way the technological and software developments of the proposed research project are integrated into the workshop(s), and describe how the workshop(s) will establish lasting connections with relevant communities (academic, industrial or otherwise).*

...

- 7d. References

Reference style/format is up to the applicant

...

8. Project plan (max 4 A4 pages for 8a – 8d)

- 8a. Requested project duration and in-kind eScience Center capacity

In-kind funding will be provided in the form of one or more Research Software Engineers (RSEs) employed by the eScience Center. The eScience Center will allocate sufficient RSEs to carry out the research proposal, depending on the project requirements and the requested eScience expertise. The project duration should be between 3 and 3,5 years. A project may be requested for an in-kind budget of a maximum of €381.510,- (approximately 3 person years of hours, depending on inflation and salary increases). A project should start at the latest 12 months after the granting decision.

Indicative project start date: ...

Indicative project end date: ...

Requested budget: ...

- 8b. Research team and key publications

Please describe the track record of the Research Team and how the team is equipped to fulfil both the research and technological aims described in 7a and 7b. Please describe:

- the LA's knowledge and experience in applying digital methodologies to research*
- recent research activities of at least one Research Team member based at a research-performing organization other than that of the LA*

...

- 8c. Key publications

Please list a maximum of 5 key publications or software releases by the Lead Applicant and/or members of the Research Team relevant to the proposal. Please indicate per publication or software release the relevance to the proposal and what the contribution of the Research Team to the publication or software release was.

...

- 8d. Work plan and deliverables

Please describe your work plan and argue why this is sufficient and appropriate to reach the project outcomes. Note that this plan will serve as a basis for the detailed project plan which will be developed together with the eScience Center at the start of the project.

Please describe:

- a realistic project structure outline including the foreseen activities of the LA, Research Team and eScience Center RSEs. Focus on "what" must be done, not on "how" this must be done*
- the timelines foreseen in this project*
- the deliverables foreseen in this project. Deliverables can include: academic publications, demonstrations, posters, presentations, software, datasets, documentation and tutorials.*

...

9. Existing Software and Data

The eScience Center expects a basic level of accessibility and quality for the software and data used in the projects it awards and collaborates on. Applicants must therefore provide convincing arguments that the software (if any) serving as starting points of the research are usable, and do not require substantial overhaul.

Your institute may employ data stewards who can advise on these topics. Additionally, information on software and data quality can be found at:

- [Choosing an open source license](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software](#)
- [Open AIRE: How to licence research data](#)
- [Open AIRE: how to make your data FAIR](#)
- [SMP decision tree tool](#)

Is there existing research software on which this project depends/builds on?

- Yes (please indicate in the SMP)
- No, the project proposes to develop new software

If there is existing software, please provide all information about this in the SMP.

Is there existing data on which this project depends/builds on?

- Yes (please indicate in list below)
- No, the project proposes to develop new data / this project does not depend on data

If there is existing data, please fill in the list below. You can copy the list if there are multiple relevant datasets. If data is currently in existence but not open access, please indicates this in the 'Location' cell of the list below (where is the data stored?, to whom is it accessible?). Please also indicate if an eScience Center member is allowed to access the data for inspection/review.

Name: ...
(Name of the dataset)

License: ...
(License, if any, e.g. CC-by 4.0, CC0)

Location: ...
(URL where the dataset can be downloaded for inspection. If data is currently in existence but not open access, please indicates where the data is stored, and to whom is it accessible)

Documentation: ...
(URL(s) with documentation, if any)

Access for inspection: ...
(Is an eScience Center member allowed to access the data for inspection? Are there any procedures that need to be followed for this access?)

Legal: ...
(Is the data GDPR /AVG sensitive information? Are there copyright concerns? Are there other concerns? If access to data requires a legal agreement, please name the responsible person that will facilitate the access at your organization)

Notes (max 100 words): ...
(Short description of the data and the state of the data or other useful notes about the data for the eScience Center)

10. Requirements regarding digital infrastructure

Applicants are asked to indicate the project's infrastructural needs (if any) and explain how they expect to fulfil those needs. In most cases, a rough estimate (order of magnitude) is sufficient. In case of doubt, please contact the eScience Center.

In all cases, a brief explanation of the choice for specific infrastructures is required. Valid options include, but are not limited to, the following:

- *The Dutch national infrastructure, including facilities offered by [SURF](#) and [DANS](#). For more information, it is advisable to contact the organizations responsible for these resources directly.*
- *Proposals may suggest the use of local, international and/or commercial (e.g. web, cloud, etc) hardware and services.*

Please describe requirements for

- *Compute services, including compute hours on CPU clusters, high-performance computing (MPI, OpenMP) and the use of accelerators (GPUs, FPGAs).*
- *Specific requirements for storage, for example, temporary disk storage and/or archival tape storage.*
- *Specific requirements regarding (high-speed) networks and data transfers.*
- *Other requirements, such as software, data sets or specialized hardware, necessary for the proposed research.*

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11. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center strictly adheres to the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU. In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must strictly apply these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

The eScience Center endorses the [Code Openness Animal Experiments](#) and the [Biosecurity Code of Conduct](#). Applicants must check whether the codes have relevance to their application. If so, the eScience Center requires applicants to endorse the code(s) and act according to these. In case of the Biosecurity Code the applicant is convinced that the knowledge presented in the application cannot lead to dual use.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the [Intellectual property rules for Netherlands eScience Center projects](#). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the [Netherlands eScience Center policy on the use of Generative AI](#). If applicable, a statement on the use of Generative AI is required. See the policy for more information.

All projects granted under this scheme must comply with the [eScience Center Special Conditions for granting](#).

- I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG), as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- I endorse and follow the Code Openness Animal Experiments (if applicable).
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing and IP. **If not ticked, please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the proposal.**
- I endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center policy on the use of Generative AI.
(if applicable, insert statement on use of Generative AI here)
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Special Conditions on Granting.
- I have informed my employing institute of the submission of this proposal, by sending a copy of the application to the formally mandated representative of my research organization (e.g. director, head of department, dean).
- I have completed this form truthfully.

Name (Lead Applicant):

Location:

Date:

Attached Documents

For the submission of this proposal the following additional documents are requested

- A Software Management Plan (**required**)

- Letters of support or intent (optional)